

Milk Borne Toxoplasmosis: Zoonotic Significance and Public Health

Concern

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Abstract

Toxoplasmosis is a disease of zoonotic significance. Toxoplasmosis in humans might happen vertically by passing the tachyzoites to the embryo across the placenta or horizontally by consumption of foods adulterated by tachyzoites and bradyzoites, unpasteurized milk, cheddar, and raw meat. As a livestock by-product, milk is collected from dairy farms and supplied through Gowallas in unhygienic manners. *T. gondii* is an opportunistic agent for patients with HIV that can damage the heart, lungs, bone marrow, vision and cause potentially fatal encephalitis in these patients. The protozoon, *T. gondii* is an obligatory intracellular parasite that can cause disorders like abortion, the birth of deformed fetuses, mummification of the fetus, weakness of new young ones, embryonic reabsorption, and other reproductive diseases in small ruminants. Worldwide, the causative agent *T. gondii* has been identified in raw milk of sheep, goat, and camel by using various approaches, i.e., latex test, direct agglutination, indirect immunofluorescence antibody test, and ELISA. The tachyzoite stage is responsible for the transmission of Toxoplasmosis infection to humans. It is also an

apprehension for pregnant mothers because tachyzoites can migrate transplacentally and cause abnormalities in human embryos.

Pakistan lacks a modern agricultural system like many other countries, which increases the prevalence of *T. gondii*. After being transported to the slaughterhouse, meat is easily contaminated with *T. gondii*. Open markets are common in Pakistan and are a cause of pathogen contamination because stray cats, mice, etc., are commonly found in the markets. There are comparatively fewer reports on the seroprevalence of *T. gondii* in distinct parts of Punjab, Pakistan. Therefore, there is a dire need to plan an epidemiological investigation in various peri-urban areas of Pakistan. The quantified prevalence of toxoplasmosis and associated risk factors will help the stakeholders, i.e., farmers, public health officials, and policymakers devise appropriate control measures against this zoonotic disease.

Keywords: Toxoplasmosis, Raw milk, sheep, goat, camel, Serodiagnosis, Zoonosis